

POLITICAL SCIENCES

PROVING THE BENEFITS OF EURO AREA MEMBERSHIP FOR THE COUNTRIES IN CENTRAL AND EASTERN EUROPE

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Abstract

Membership in the euro area should presumably bring benefits to member countries. But these can only be proven in a comparison between countries on either side of the "currency frontier". The "Visegrad countries" - Poland, the Czech Republic, Hungary, Slovakia and Slovenia - are selected as comparable countries with similar cultural, social and economic characteristics. The combination of sociological and economic indicators should overcome the limitations of the technocratic approach. However, tracking these indicators over the period from 2009 to 2021 does not prove the advantages of euro area membership.

Keywords: euro area, advantages, indicators, comparison

JEL: F15

Introduction

The euro area has existed since 1999. Bulgaria is obliged to join it under the EU Accession Treaty. This, however, depends on meeting pre-set requirements for financial sustainability, and government policy in this respect can, given the political will, delay the process indefinitely. Indeed, eurozone entry is a goal for most political forces in Bulgaria and hence for official policy. Support from the population, however, is hesitant. There is currently a debate about the advantages and disadvantages of Bulgaria's possible membership in the euro area. The arguments are mainly fought at the political level and there are devoid of a thorough scientific analysis. According to the official position expressed on the European Union's website, the euro area should ensure better functioning of the European economy, as well as create more jobs and greater prosperity for EU citizens. The specific benefits alternate as follows:

- Easy price comparisons between countries, which increases competition between businesses, thereby benefiting consumers;
- Price stability;
- The euro makes it easier, cheaper and safer for businesses to buy and sell in the euro area and to trade with the rest of the world;
- Increased economic stability and growth;
- Better integrated and therefore more efficient financial markets;
- Greater influence in the global economy;
- A tangible symbol of European identity²

For Bulgaria, which has been under a monetary council since 1997, some of these advantages are in place. In contrast, the debate also highlights other benefits: lower interest rates on government borrowing, increased investment, higher economic growth, lower transaction fees on imports and exports, and a better credit rating for the country.

But the objections to Bulgaria's entry into the eurozone overlook one particular risk: there is no mechanism for its exit if it turns out that the expected favourable consequences occur. While the expected benefits may be felt, the opposite is also possible. However, there is no way to revise the decision if it turns out to be wrong.

To overcome this quandary, I propose a simple and straightforward method for checking whether and to what extent the expected benefits of euro area membership actually occur. The method is based on a simple comparative analysis. It is made possible by the fact that there are EU member states that are not part of the euro area and show no intention of joining it in the foreseeable future. This suggests that the benefits are not indisputable. A comparison with similar eurozone member states over a sufficiently long period can prove or challenge the advantages that membership brings with it. More appropriate for Bulgaria is the example of the former socialist countries in Central and Eastern Europe, which had to reform to capitalism and liberal democracy on the way to joining the European Union. By the way, the result of the study may be of interest to some other EU member states, which for now remain outside the eurozone.

Another limitation: the analysis covers data up to and including 2021. Data for 2022 show a sharp change in many indicators. The consequences of the crisis events of the summer of 2021 (e.g. inflation) and the whole of 2022 (e.g. war and immigrant flow) are yet to be clarified, it remains to be seen how lasting they will be. The findings of the current study should be attributed to a relatively quiet period of development. An abrupt and sustained change in framework conditions requires another application of the method proposed here over a subsequent long period of at least ten years.

² https://european-union.europa.eu/institutions-law-budget/euro/benefits_bg

1. Methodology

The method proposed here for assessing the implications of a country's participation/ non-participation in the euro area involves comparing key societal development indicators for a group of countries on both sides of the "currency frontier". Since, according to the theory of optimal currency areas (Mundell, 1961), positive effects occur primarily when individual economies with similar degrees of development are brought together. This implies purposive selection. To obtain more accurate results, however, comparative indicators must go beyond purely economic ones, otherwise the limitations of the technocratic approach would prevail. It is assumed that the economy serves societal development objectives and not the other way around. So the broadest social indicators have to be studied in order to fix the impact of euro area membership on overall societal progress. Each indicator has its own limitations, so combining more indicators into a common group should reduce unavoidable distortions and inaccuracies to an acceptable level.

1.1. Selection of indicators

The social indicators selected here are interrelated:

1. **Quality of life**, including health, education, demography, economic conditions, environmental conditions, hygienic living conditions, employment, security and the exercise of constitutional rights. This is a fairly comprehensive indicator that includes quantifiable, objective data. (The problem in the present case has been the difficulty in finding sufficient data for individual countries over the entire 12-year period.) A derivative of this indicator is the **Human Development Index** measured by the United Nations, which focuses mainly on life expectancy, educational attainment, and GDP per capita.

2. **Human Happiness Index**, measured by the World Population Review. This is a purely subjective perception that sometimes produces surprisingly high scores in societies that do not put material consumption first. Societies in the highly developed EU countries are at the top of Maslow's (1954) pyramid, in the area of 'development needs'. However, a decrease in the indicator in these countries may also indicate a decrease at the bottom of the pyramid, i.e. an increase in material hardship during economic stagnation.

3. **Demographic picture** - derived independently, this indicator alone is not sufficient for general conclusions. In general, an increase in population is associated with an increased quality of life, but a reduction can also be a positive sign - e.g. reduced demand for unskilled labour at the expense of highly skilled labour in the transition to intensive economic growth, including mechanisation of agriculture, robotization in industry, etc.

4. **Unemployment** - this is not primarily (much less solely) an economic indicator. It is a general social indicator that enters into the determination of the quality of life, it also has a direct relationship with the demographic picture. Since employment not only provides material consumption but also satisfies developmental needs (according to Maslow), its indicators fit

in several places in the overall picture, e.g. it is present in the happiness indicator.

5. **Inequality coefficient, Gini** - it is also directly related to the first two indicators and especially important in egalitarian societies with a long socialist tradition, which turn out to be the countries considered below.

Economic indicators - here they come, interrelated:

1. **GDP per capita** is a more important indicator, filled with more content on actual production and consumption;

2. **Government debt** is among the main indicators of financial stability. A healthy upper limit of 60% of GDP has been set for the euro area since its planning. (Let's note, by the way, that since the financial crisis the euro area has averaged about 50% above this indicator.)

3. **Inflation** is another key indicator of financial stability. Low inflation is, in fact, the sine qua non that Germany, the economic centre of the EU, set during the planning of the euro area.

4. **Trade balance**: the possibility of exchange rate changes has a direct link to it and it is important to track to what extent (non-)participation in a currency area affects foreign trade, including the redirection of trade flows;

5. For a more complete picture on the development of external economic linkages I add the **balance of payments**, with the inclusion of capital flows. It should complete the picture of overall economic development.

The idea in tracking the two sets of indicators for the period from 2009 (Slovakia's entry into the euro area) to 2021 is simple: if euro area membership brings benefits, it should be evident in the aggregate. The period covers an economic cycle that includes the acute financial crisis of 2009-2012 and the subsequent recovery period. It is sufficiently long to allow for the identification of lasting trends and gives sufficient weight to the conclusions - the effect of (not) using the common currency is traceable under both favourable and unfavourable conditions.

1.2. Selection of countries

For the purposes of this publication, five countries are included - Poland, the Czech Republic, Slovakia, Hungary ("Visegrad Group") and Slovenia. They are quite close geographically (they all border each other), culturally, with a common historical past in many respects, and with a similar degree of economic development and similar indicators at the beginning of the period under study. This allows a fair comparison having in mind justified criticism that twenty years after the introduction of the euro no real convergence has been achieved between the member states. (Carlo Klein, 2022) This includes countries entered simultaneously the European Union after a similar period of transition to capitalism and liberal democracy. According to the accession treaty, all five countries are obliged to adopt the common currency, but they have the freedom to choose when and how to meet the ex-ante requirements for financial discipline and when to apply for eurozone membership, taking into account their national interests. Slovenia has been in the euro area since 2007, Slovakia since 2009, and Hungary, the Czech Republic and

Poland do not intend to join for the time being, postponing the issue indefinitely. In early 2021, support for the euro in Polish public opinion exceeded 55% for the first time. At the same time, approval for the common currency in Hungary was 69%, but in the Czech Republic it was only 33%. The countries listed are relatively small, with populations between 2.8 and 10.7 million (Poland is an exception with 37.8 million). The size is only relevant for a very limited range of goods and services for local use, giving a small advantage in the case

of the Czech Republic and Hungary and a larger one for Poland. Their economies are therefore open: most of their external trade is in the EU's Single market. The share of this trade is between 63% for Slovenia and 80% for Slovakia. For all the selected countries, Germany is the main trading partner, with geographical proximity further facilitating trade. (The Czech Republic and Poland share a border with Germany.)

Extra and Intra EU trade in goods, 2021
(imports plus exports, % share of total trade)

Source: Eurostat (Easy Comext : DS-018995)

Figure 1: Share of merchandise trade in the EU Internal Market by country

Source: Eurostat

All of them seek to occupy the advantageous position of semi-peripheral member states in order to maximise the benefits of their EU membership. Culturally, they are very close - they are predominantly Catholic countries, parts of the Habsburg Empire for different lengths of time, which puts its mark on the political and work ethic. Slovaks and Czechs are ethnically and linguistically very close, there is a kinship with Slovenes and Poles within the larger Slavic community. According to Minkov and Hofstede's (2007) observations, these societies are 'tribal', i.e. susceptible to corruption. They are 'egalitarian', which, among other things, precludes a willingness to submit to 'imperial institutions' in Brussels. These societies are also not described as 'compassionate', which explains the negative attitude towards cultural alien immigrants, which has been a constant problem in the EU since 2015. The socialist past retains among the majority of citizens an attachment to the welfare state model. These common

features also explain a lot of common political positions.

Attitudes towards European integration for these countries are a matter of civilisational belonging and EU membership is invariably highly supported. However, the Visegrad countries have shown signs of Euroscepticism. These are linked to the protection of national interests and a reluctance to fully surrender sovereignty to the supranational institutions of the Union. In conservative Catholic societies, there is a cultural resistance to the markedly extreme liberal ideology in Western Europe. This resistance is most pronounced and enduring, including at the political level, in Poland and Hungary. They do not accept integration in its entirety and rule out the its development of unification towards a federal superstate. However, their position as net beneficiaries of the common budget of the Union does not allow for the consideration of exit options.

Figure 2: Net financial contribution to the EU by country

Source: European Commission, <https://www.statista.com/chart/18794/net-contributors-to-eu-budget/>

The economic positions and respective interests of the five countries are similar, especially in the case of the Visegrad Four, but the expectations for it to take shape institutionally and to consistently defend common positions within the EU are not yet coming true. There is an idea that Slovenia should be invited into the Group, but so far this is not happening either. In any case, the commonalities between the selected five countries are too many and make them a suitable subject for comparative analysis.

2. Results and reading

The results for the period 2009-2021 shown in the following tables establish the following:

The populations of all 5 countries considered show stagnation - slight growth in Slovakia and Slovenia or slight decline in Poland and Hungary. In 12 years of membership, emigration to more developed EU countries has been successfully curbed, while immigration, especially from non-EU countries, is not encouraged in any way. Net migration is highest in 2021 in the Czech

Republic at 0.5%, followed by Slovenia at 0.3. For the remaining countries, the indicators are even closer to 0. Immigration has a direct relationship with quality of life, which is relatively high in the Czech Republic and Slovenia and sufficiently high in the others, with the differences not significant. The "happiness" indicators are close, with an overall slight improvement. There is not much difference in the Gini coefficient, with slight fluctuations in both directions. The coefficient for all is relatively low and guarantees social stability. Overall, fluctuations are within a narrow range. For the period under review, unemployment shows a positive trend, with only Slovakia remaining above the accepted healthy ceiling of 6%. In the Human Development Index, all countries deteriorated, with the exception of Poland, but remained in the group of highly developed countries. The most serious regression is in Hungary and Slovakia. From the overall review of the indicators, no conclusion can be drawn about a noticeable advantage of the euro area member states over the others.

Table 1

Comparative social indicators 2000-2020

	Population, million	HDI, place	Unemployment	Coefficient Gini	Happiness, 2013-2021	Quality of life by 2022, №
Poland	38,2 – 37,8*	36 - 34	8,2 - 3,4	31,4 – 26,8	5,8 – 6,1	40
Czech Republic	10,5 - 10,5	28 - 32	6,7 – 2,9	26,2 - 24,8	6,3 - 7	21
Hungary	10 - 9,7	36 - 47	10 – 4,1	24,7 – 27,6	4,8 – 6,1	39
Slovakia	5,38 - 5,4	40 - 45	12 - 6,7	24,8 - 21	6 – 6,4	32
Slovenia	2 – 2,1	22 - 23	5,9 – 4,4	22,7 - 23	6 – 6,6	18

* Red colour indicates improvement of the indicator, blue - deterioration. In grey are the euro area countries.

Source: own development, data from <https://www.macrotrends.net/countries/>, <https://fred.stlouisfed.org/series/SIPOVGINIDNK>, <https://worldpopulationreview.com/country-rankings/happiest-countries-in-the-world>, World Population Review, <https://countryeconomy.com/hdi?year=2009>, <https://www.statista.com/statistics/263705/>, <https://countryeconomy.com/demography/gini-index/>, <https://countryeconomy.com/demography/world-happiness-index/poland>

In the economic indicators, the movement of GDP over the period shows almost complete synchrony. The fluctuations since the onset of the 2008 global economic crisis have been very similar.

Figure 3: GDP growth of the selected countries
Poland – 679,4 млрд.\$ (439,7), Czech Republic

Source: <https://www.google.com/search>, data from World Bank

The increase in GDP per capita (purchasing power parity) is between 1.5 and 2 times, with the Czech Republic performing best and Slovakia performing worst. Adjusting for inflation does not change the picture - the inflation rate for the whole group of countries is low, averaging between 2% and 3.3% per year, highest in Hungary. The trade balance for the period is generally positive - strong growth for Poland, persistently high for the Czech Republic, positive with a maximum towards 2015-2016 and weak indicators at the beginning and end of the period for the other countries. Slovakia has the worst performance, including negative indicators at the beginning and end of the period. In combination, the balance of payments favours Slovenia with the best indicators over the period. In the overall similar picture, Poland stands out with its sharp fluctuations and predominantly negative

values. Data on government external debt as a share of GDP give an advantage to Poland and the Czech Republic, which remain below the 60% ceiling allowed by the Maastricht criteria for financial discipline. For Hungary, debt is persistently higher, at around 70-74%, but lower compared with the Eurozone average. At the end of the period under review, Slovakia exceeds this indicator by a small margin, while for Slovenia the indicator deteriorates sharply towards the middle of the period and remains above 74% at the end. Euro area membership does not promote financial discipline in this case, rather the opposite. The case of Slovakia confirms the observation (albeit weaker) that sovereign countries in the euro area tend to issue debt in a currency (euro) over which they have no control (De Grauwe, 2021).

Source: Figure 4: Balance of payments, https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/BN.CAB.XOKA.CD?locations=PL-SI-SK-HU-CZ&name_desc=true

https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.PCAP.PP.CD?locations=PL-CZ-SK-HU-SI&name_desc=true
Source: Figure 5: GDP growth, per capita, PPP,

Table 2

Comparative economic indicators 2000-2021

	GDP growth, per capita, PPP, \$	Inflation	Trade balance, \$ billion	Balance of payments, \$ billion	Sovereign debt, % of GDP
Poland	19 239 – 37 836 (x 1,96)	5 – -1 – 5, average 2,5	-4,3 – 28,3	- 18,56 – 17,3 – -4,6	50 – 45,6 – 57
Czech Republic	27 761 – 59 324 (x 2,13)	0 – 5, average 2,5	8,1 – 16,8 – 8,6 (...)	-4,9 – 3,46 – -2,3	33,4 – 42 – 30
Hungary	20 729 – 36 752 (x 1,77)	3 – -1 – 5, average 3,3	4,5 – 10,8 – 1,4 (...)	-0,9 – 5,85 – -7,2	75 – 65,5 – 76,8
Slovakia	23 080 – 33 010 (x 1,43)	2 – -1 – 5, average 2,5	-0,15 – 5,5 – -0,74	-3 – 1,8 – -2,9	36,4 – 55 – 63
Slovenia	27 537 – 43 602 (x 1,58)	-1 – 3 – -1, average 2	0,7 – 4,9 – 3,3	-0,5 – 4,6 – 2,37	34,5 – 82,6 – 74,7

Source: own development, data from IMF, <https://www.macrotrends.net/countries/BEL/poland/trade-balance-deficit>, https://tradingeconomics.com/hungary/inflation-cpi*, <https://tradingeconomics.com/hungary/government-debt-to-gdp>, <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.PCAP.PP.CD?locations=BE>

Conclusion

Summing up the results of the social and economic indicators, we find the following: for the whole period under study, the overall progress of the Czech Republic and Slovenia is the most remarkable. Poland has better macroeconomic indicators than Slovakia and Hungary, but this does not give it a perceptible advantage in overall human development indicators. Hungary is slightly behind compared to the whole top five. Overall, the performance of the countries under consideration remains similar throughout the period under review, and the group as a whole shows a loss of ground compared to the more developed countries, both in the EU and in the world as a whole.

The important conclusion is: **euro area membership does NOT affect development in the period 2009-2021**. Non-participation does not prevent the successful development of the Czech Republic and Poland. Participation in the euro area does not help Slovakia to perform better in the period studied, while Slovenia simply maintains an initial higher level. There is no evidence that the single currency helps any of the countries under study to gain a distinct advantage over their

close neighbours, which hold on to their national currencies. Clearly, the factors for successful development are different. The eurozone shows no measurable impact on increasing economic stability and growth - the important advantages to be measured and highlighted by the official position expressed on the European Union's website.

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